

EXPLANATION OF THE PROCESSES OF STRUGGLE FOR POWER IN MOVAROUNNAH IN 1358-1370 IN HISTORICAL SOURCES

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Abstract

This article analyzes the processes of struggle for power in Movarounnahr in 1358-1370, their causes and consequences based on historical sources. The views of Ghiyasuddin Ali, Nizamuddin Shami, Muiniddin Natanzi, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Fasih Khawafi and Ibn Arabshah on the events of these years were studied on the basis of comparative, critical and historical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

A number of historical sources have an incomparable place in the study of the history of the weakening of the rule of the Mongol khans and the struggle of local begs to seize power in Movarounnahr.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The first to write the history of Amir Temur was the historian Ghiyaziddin Ali, in his work "The Indian Invasion of India" he talked about the Indian campaign of 1399 [1]. The work contains almost no information on the issue we are researching. The author, Amir Temur, limited himself to noting that Movarounnahr was united around the capital city of Samarkand, and focused on illuminating the activities of Sahibqiron in the later period[2,28].

One of the first sources that played an important role in the study of the history of this period is the work "Zafarnama" by Nizamiddin Shami. This work is valuable because it was written according to the order of Amir Temur and was presented to Sahibqiran and received a positive evaluation. Some studies have been conducted in source studies about the life and work of Nizamiddin Shami, including the work "Zafarnama" [3].

In his work, the author begins the detailed account of historical events with the murder of Movarounnahr emir Kazaghan. The transition of the position of the emir of Movarounnahr to the emir Abdullah and his removal from power as a result of disputes, after that the events of the headships that began in the country, and the division of the regions by the emirs, are consistently described. It is noteworthy that the information about the composition of the emirs who gained power in Movarounnahr regions served as a basis for historical sources written in the later period [28-29]. One of the information in this work, which is hardly found in other sources, is that Qutlugh Temur, the murderer of Emir Kazaghan, is from Oranaityan tribe, and Emir Kaykhusraf showed bravery in capturing and punishing him[4,28]. Muiniddin Natanziy Qutlug limited himself to describing Temur as "some kind of Mongol" and did not provide information about his punishment[5,50]. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, noting that Qutlugh was from the Airat tribe of Temur, noted that he was captured near Kunduz, but did not specify the identity of those who carried out this deed[6,110]. Fasih Khavafi did not mention the punishment and origin of Kutlug Temur[7,110].

In "Zafarnama" by Nizamiddin Shami, the Mongolian Khan Tughluq Temur Khan's Movarounnahr campaigns, the attitude of local beys towards these campaigns, Amir Temur's goal of going to the service of the Mongolian Khan, mutual disputes between local beys and many issues such as the rise of Amir Husayn's position are detailed[4].

Mu'iniddin Natanzi's work "Muntakhab ut-tawarikhi Muini" is one of the important sources in the study of the history of the struggle for power in Movarounnahr in the years 1358-1370. The life of Muiniddin Natanzi and the researches about this work reveal the history of the writing of the work [8]. In the work, after the death of Amir Kazaghan, his son Amir Abdullah was put on the throne, the usurpation of power by Amir Bayon Sulduz, Tughluq Temurkhan's campaigns in Movarounnahr, political processes that took place in Movarounnahr during the reign of Ilyashoja, and the coming to power of Amir Husayn. , the Battle of Loy, the activities of generals, and the struggle for power between Amir Husayn and Amir Temur were told in a special spirit in "Zafarnama" by Nizamiddin Shami and Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi[9]. Because the author tried to write his work in the type of general history, we can feel the relative neutrality and objectivity in the narrative of events more widely compared to other works.

Another difference of the work from other historical sources is that it contains information about the acquisition of power by the warlords of Samarkand, their struggle against the Mongols, the fact that the main leader of the warlords was Mavlonzade, and Mavlonzade's relationship with Amir Temur [10]. This information plays an important role in the in-depth analysis of the history of this period and in drawing reasonable scientific conclusions. While he established his influence in Tashkent and Sayram regions, Amir Temur also tried to use their help in the fight against Amir Husayn. But seeing that the Mongols, who came to help, instead of fighting against the troops of Amir Husayn, began to plunder the Jizzakh region, Sahibgiron himself was forced to drive them out, it is emphasized by Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi. The analysis of information in "Zafarnoma" shows that as a result of mutual wars in Movarounnahr, the Mongol emirs managed to bring the territories of Tashkent region under their control[4].

Fasih Khavafi's "Mujmali Fasihi" is one of the important sources for studying the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period. A number of studies have been created in our source studies about this work and its author, which is distinguished by its wealth of short and accurate factual information [14].

In the work, you can find many valuable facts and information related to our research, including the reasons for the crisis of Amir Abdullah's power, Amir Husain's struggles against Tughluq Temurkhan, disagreements between Amir Temur and Amir Husain "Mud Battle" the information that it was before [15] is noteworthy.

One of the works that contains information about the history of Amir Timur and the Timurid era is Ibn Arabshah's "Ajaib al-maqdur fi history of Taimur". This source was translated into Uzbek and published[16].

In his work, Ibn Arabshah provided interesting information about the activities of a number of emirs who played a leading role in the mutual wars in Movarounnahr. Information about Amir Temur's acquaintance with Amir Husain, the emergence of kinship ties between them, the borders of the territories under Amir Husain's control, the four ministers of Amir Husain, Amir Temur's alliance with the governors of Badakhshan against Husain, other historical sources It is important to analyze and critically analyze [17]. The fact that the

author lived in Movarounnahr for a certain time allowed him to have enough information about the geography of this region [18].

CONCLUSION

It can be said that the role of historical sources is very important in studying the history of the struggle for power in Movarounnahr in 1358-1370. Comparative analysis of the information presented in them, taking into account the personal attitude of the authors to the past events and events, by critically approaching the personal opinions expressed by them, is one of the urgent tasks facing historians.

The information presented in different chapters of the work "Muntakhab ut-tawarikhi Muini" is distinguished by the fact that it complements each other. For example, the author, as we said above, described the murderer of Amir Kazaghan as "some kind of Mongol" at the beginning of his work, but in another chapter of the source he fills it in a little, so that this additional information not found in other sources. The fact that the author Qutlug' Temur belongs to the clan of one of the Hazara emirs, that he married the sister of Qutlug' Turkon Ago, the wife of Emir Kazaghan, and that he was expelled from the Emirate for oppressing his Hazaras, at the request of Emir Kazaghan Qutlug' Turkon Ago despite this, he states that the guilty person has not repented of his sin, that is why Kutlugh Temur took the life of the ruler" [11,68-72]. Based on this, it is important to critically compare the information provided when using this source from other chapters of the work to draw a scientific conclusion.

One of the important information in the work is related to the fate of Amir Abdullah. Many sources state that after the rebellion of Amir Bayon Sulduz and Amir Haji Barlos, the defeated amir Abdullah left Movarounnahr and there is no clear information about his later life. But Muiniddin Natanzi noted that Amir Abdullah and several of his brothers were executed, that his grave was located in the city of Munk, that his brother named Sultan Mahmud took refuge in Mongolia, and that his nephew Amir Husayn fled to Kunduz and Baghlan and took possession of that land. reaches [11,92-93]. This information is valuable because it is not found in other historical sources and it greatly helps the research of historical processes.

Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi's work "Zafarnama" is also one of the important sources of research. Several scientific works have been carried out in the field of source studies about the life and creative activity of the author, the history of writing and distribution of the work "Zafarnama", translations [12].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

"Zafarnoma" is also significant as the most detailed source of the history of internecine wars and the struggle for power in Movarounnahr in 1358-1370. Although the main part of the work begins with the coverage of the activities of Amir Kazaganbek, the center of the subsequent events is mainly Amir Temur, and the events are narrated around him, depending on the history of Sahibqiran to one degree or another. This creates the need for a critical approach to the author's comments when using this source to explain the struggle for power in Movarounnahr.

One of the important aspects of the work for our research is that it contains the struggles of Amir Husayn against Bayon Suzduz, the emergence and development of the conflict between Amir Temur and Amir Haji Barlos, between Amir Temur and Amir Hizr Yasavuri. Most of the information about the past battles is not widely covered in other

sources[13,22-25]. The Kumushkand truce concluded between Amir Temur and Amir Husain, as well as the information about the structure of the amirs who opposed and supported it are also important [13,56-58]. These data also make it possible to determine the reaction of the emirs to the long-term struggle for power.

From the information given in "Zafarnoma", it is understood that some emirs of Mongolia tried to use the struggle for power in Movarounnahr for their own interests. They entered the country by offering their support to various Mowarounnahr emirs, tried to plunder the people and bring some areas under their control. As a result of such assistance, the governor of Khojand, Bahrom Jaloyir, was happy for some time

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